

Supporting Information for

Resolving the tectonic setting of South China in the late Paleozoic

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Introduction

We provided detailed methods and analytical procedures in the text below. Supplemental Figure S1-S3 and data Table S1 to S5 are uploaded separately.

Text S1 Analytical Methods

Detrital zircons were handpicked randomly from heavy-mineral concentrates. Zircon crystals were mounted in epoxy resin and polished to section the crystals in half for analysis. Cathodoluminescence (CL) imaging was used to exhibit zircon internal structure. The U-Pb age dating of detrital zircons was conducted by LA-ICP-MS at the Tianjin Center of Geological Survey, China Geological Survey, using the method proposed by (Liu et al., 2010) with a beam diameter of 35 μm . Zircon 91500 and Plešovice were used as external standards for U-Pb dating calibration. Glass NIST 610 was used as external standards for trace element calibration. For zircons younger than 1000 Ma, the $^{206}\text{Pb}/^{238}\text{U}$ ages are adopted, and the $^{207}\text{Pb}/^{206}\text{Pb}$ ages are used

for grains older than 1000 Ma in order to reduce the effect of Pb loss (Compston et al., 1992).

Only analyses with age concordance between 90 % and 110 % are incorporated in the discussion below.

Zircon Hf isotopic data were conducted by LA-MC-ICP-MS at Nanjing FocuMS Technology Co. Ltd. The experiments were performed on scientific instruments with the combination of *RESOLUTION LR* laser-ablation system (Canberra, Australia) and *Nu Plasma II* MC-ICP-MS (Wrexham, Wales, UK). The 193 nm ArF excimer was focused zircon surface with fluence of 4.5 J/cm². Each acquisition comprised 20 s' background stage (gas blank) and the followed 40 s' laser ablation stage with spot diameter of 50 µm at 9 Hz repetition rate. Helium (370 ml/min) was applied as carrier gas. Standard zircons (including GJ-1, 91500, Plešovice, Mud Tank, and Penglai) were intercalated as the quality controls every fifteen analyses. Measured Hf isotope ratios were corrected for mass fractionation using an exponential law with $^{179}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf} = 0.7325$. The correction of isobaric interference of ^{176}Yb on ^{176}Hf is the key point in obtaining precise and accurate $^{176}\text{Hf}/^{177}\text{Hf}$ values for in-situ zircon Hf isotopic measurements. $^{176}\text{Yb}/^{172}\text{Yb}$ ratio of 0.5887 (Vervoort et al., 2004) and the β^{Yb} value obtained from the sample spot analysis itself were applied for the Yb correction.

Captions of Figure S1-S3

Figure S1. Fusulinid biostratigraphy of the Outanddi section. For legend of the lithological column, see main text Fig. 1. a. *Fusulina ozawai* Rauser, 1951, sample from -9.0 m of OTD section; b. *Fusulinella helenae* Rauser, 1951, sample from -9.0 m of OTD section; c. *Beedeina elshanica* (Putrya, 1948), sample from -3.3 m of OTD section; d. *Fusulinella praecolaniae* Safonova, 1951, sample from -1.4 m of OTD section; e. *Fusulina schellwieni* (Staff, 1912), sample from 2.0 m of OTD section; f. *Fusulina lanceolata* Lee et Chen, 1930, sample from 19.7 m of OTD section; g. *Fusulina okensis* Rauser, 1951, sample from 19.6 m of OTD section; h. *Fusulinella colaniae* Lee et Chen, 1930, sample from 23.8 m of OTD section; i. *Fusulina pakhrensis* Rauser, 1951, sample from 23.21 m of OTD section; j. *Fusulina quasicylindrica compacta* Sheng, 1958, sample from 20.45 m of OTD section; k. *Fusulina nytvica* Safonova, 1951, sample from 26.55 m of OTD section.

Figure S2. Cathodoluminescence images of typical detrital zircons. The yellow circles and yellow values denote the U-Pb age analytical spots and U-Pb ages. The red circles and red values denote the Hf isotope analytical spots and $\epsilon\text{Hf}(t)$ values.

Figure S3. (a) Pb-Th plot of the ten youngest detrital zircons (red solid circles), after Wang et al.

(2012) and reference therein. (b) Zircon trace element Th/U versus Nb/Hf diagram for the ten youngest detrital zircons, after Qi et al. (2021).

Captions of Table S1-S5

Table S1. Detrital zircon U-Pb ages of sandstones from the Outangdi section.

Table S2. Detrital zircon Hf isotopic data of sandstones from the Outangdi section.

Table S3. Detrital zircon trace element compositions of sandstones from the Outangdi section.

Table S4. Detrital zircon U-Pb age data compiled in figure 3c.

Table S5. Detrital zircon *in situ* Hf isotopic data plotted in figure 3d.